

Resource-efficient and climate-friendly design of concrete structures through advanced structural safety concepts

Ramon Hingorani, Jochen Köhler

Norwegian University of Science and Technology (NTNU), Trondheim, Norway

Contact: ramon.hingorani@ntnu.no

Abstract

As the bones and muscles of our built environment, engineering structures support all kind of societal activities. However, they consume huge amounts of resources and significantly contribute to impact on our environment. Structural design codes play an important matter in this regard since they regulate the use of materials by use of prescribed decision rules. These relatively simple and generalised rules offer significant potential for improvement. Grounded on risk-based optimisation approaches, this paper explores this potential in connection with the design of reinforced concrete floor systems. Assuming a large variety of realistic design situations, representative sets of such members are defined and designed according to the semi-probabilistic safety concept in the Eurocodes. The benefits of a risk-informed structural design compared to the use of these standardised decision rules is demonstrated in terms of material consumption and CO₂ emissions.

Keywords: Sustainability, embodied greenhouse gas emissions, optimisation, structural reliability, risk-based design, risk-informed decision making, structural design codes, concrete structures

1 Introduction

Many current and future challenges are related to the efficient management of limited financial and natural resources or the appropriate mitigation of consequences due to climate change. Engineering structures play a fundamental role in this regard since they consume large amounts of raw materials and contribute significantly to greenhouse gas emissions worldwide, e.g. [1-4]. As the challenges will become bigger, the demand for innovative and sustainable solutions well beyond traditional structural engineering practice will increase.

Structural design codes, which regulate the safety of our built environment and the corresponding use of structural materials, are crucial in this context. They feature safety concepts that are highly generalized to make them simple and

applicable to a large variety of structures at the same time. This leads to structures that are sufficiently safe and functional, but where structural material is not utilized in an optimal manner. For a sustainable built environment, this is not good enough. We need to unlock the potential offered by risk-based decision approaches in order to utilize our resources in structural design procedures as efficient as possible. Intensively discussed in the scientific literature over the past decades, e.g. [5-8], and by now supported by standardized guidance [9], these approaches facilitate optimized solutions such that a balance is achieved between a specific structural safety level and the corresponding resources invested.

In the past, the objective of such optimisation procedures was mainly of economic nature, i.e. with focus on minimising costs. While this

approach may contribute likewise to mitigation of material consumption and greenhouse gas emissions, it was recently suggested to explore the potential benefits of addressing such environmental objectives explicitly, since the corresponding optimum might significantly deviate from the solution based on an economic decision framework [10, 11].

On the grounds of an emission-based objective function (section 2), the paper assesses the material and greenhouse gas emission saving potential of a risk-informed design of floor structures with reinforced concrete members. The environmental benefits compared to the application of the standardised design rules (Partial Factor Method) as defined in the Eurocodes [12] are demonstrated and discussed (section 3).

2 Optimisation framework

2.1 Objective function

Taking the widely accepted economic optimisation framework proposed by Rackwitz [5] as a basis, an objective function for a risk-informed design based on carbon emissions (CE) is being defined, see Eqn. (1). In this formulation, the benefits have been considered independent of the decision parameter p (e.g. a cross-section dimension), wherefore the optimization problem simplifies to the determination of $p = p_{opt}$ which minimizes the expected total emissions CE_{tot} associated with a specific decision, as illustrated in Figure 1. The total emissions CE_{tot} are constituted by the sum of the emissions related to investments into safety- (CE_s) and those expected in consequence of a failure event (CE_f). The former are defined as the sum of the emissions associated with the production and construction-stage CE_c (cradle-to-site emissions), in the following referred to as *construction-related emissions*, and the expected emissions due to structural obsolescence, CE_o .

$$p_{opt} = \arg \min_p (CE_c + CE_o + CE_f) \quad (1)$$

In Eqn. (2), the construction-related emissions CE_c are defined as the sum of term $CE_1 p$, which is proportional to the decision parameter p , and a p -independent constant CE_o . The expected emissions

due to failure (CE_f) and obsolescence (CE_o) defined by, respectively, Eqns. (3) and (4), are estimated based on the assumption that structures are continuously renewed either after failure or after becoming obsolete respectively. A discussion and justification of this assumption can be found in [5]. Emissions in consequence of reconstruction are multiplied by the yearly obsolescence-rate ω resulting in the expected yearly obsolescence emissions (CE_o). The expected yearly failure emissions (CE_f) are defined as the sum of reconstruction-related emissions CE_c and indirect failure emissions H , independent of p , multiplied by the yearly failure rate $\lambda P_f(p)$. Like costs, future emissions are to be discounted, see e.g. [13]. The net present value of the sum of annual expectations with the annual interest rate i is computed by utilizing the asymptotic solution expressed by Eqn. (5).

$$CE_c = CE_o + CE_1 p \quad (2)$$

$$CE_o = CE_c \frac{\omega}{i} \quad (3)$$

$$CE_f = (CE_c + H) \frac{\lambda P_f(p)}{i} \quad (4)$$

$$\sum_{\tau=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{(1+i)^\tau} = \frac{1}{i} \quad (5)$$

Figure 1. Illustration of the carbon emission-based optimization principle and deviations $\delta_{CE,tot}$ and δ_p from the minimum total emissions ($CE_{tot,min}$) and optimal decision parameter (p_{opt}), respectively.

2.2 Life safety constraints

While the objective function given by Eqn. (1) pursues an optimum design from an environmental perspective (in this case related to embodied greenhouse gas emissions), it does not guarantee that this optimum (p_{opt}) is consistent with the societal preferences in regard to life safety investments. As illustrated in Figure 2 this can be considered by imposing a corresponding acceptance criterion to the failure probability, $P_{f,opt} < P_{f,acc}$, e.g. based on the marginal life-saving costs principle, see [7, 9] for further guidance.

Figure 2. Illustration of life-safety (LS) acceptance criteria as constraint to the optimisation (opt)

2.3 Environmental saving potential

The resource- and emission saving potential of the described optimisation framework in relation to the sub-optimal decisions based on the standardised design rules defined in structural codes and standards, such as the Eurocodes, is illustrated in Figure 1. Generally, these sub-optimal decisions, represented by the dots, entail a certain deviation, in terms of the expected total emissions CE_{tot} from their respective optimum, $\delta_{CE,tot}$. Further, it is of interest, how the sub-optimal solutions deviate from the optimum in terms of the decision parameter p , which is representative of the material consumption and of the associated embodied greenhouse gas emissions at the structural design stage, i.e. when the decision is made. In contrast to $\delta_{CE,tot}$, the deviation δ_p can theoretically occur on both sides of the optimum p_{opt} , see Figure 1.

3 Case study

3.1 Structural system and loads

The case study assumes two different types of floor systems in office buildings (Figure 3): A) RC floor beams which provide support to one-way RC slabs spanning in the direction perpendicular to the beam orientation and B) a floor system where the slab is supported by T-beams. In both systems, the beams of span L are simply supported and spaced at a distance D .

Figure 3. Sketch of the floor systems: A) RC beams supporting one-way RC slabs; B) RC T-beams

Permanent loads g acting on the beams include the structural self-weight (g_{sw}) of both the beams, $g_{sw,b}$ (limited to the web in case of the T-beam system) and the slabs, $g_{sw,sl}$, as well as the weight of non-structural permanent loads, g_{nspl} , including the flooring and roofing system attached to the slabs. In addition, the beams sustain a uniformly distributed imposed load q (Figure 4).

Figure 4. Structural system and loads

3.2 Limit state function

Bending failure at mid-span of the beams is considered. The limit state function (LSF) represents the state of equilibrium between acting and resisting bending moments at mid-span of the beams, respectively M_E and M_R . These are specified in Eqns. (6) and (7), where Θ_E and Θ_R denote the corresponding model uncertainties. Variable Θ_q in Eqn. (6) represents the uncertainties associated with the imposed load model. The bending resistance M_R is specified in a generic way such that it represents both systems analysed, A and B (Figure 3). In the latter, the beam flange contributes to resistance of the concrete compression stresses over an effective width $b=b_{eff}$ according to EN1992-1-1 [14], in the former $b=b_w$, see Eqn. (8). The reinforcement ratio ρ_s is defined accordingly in Eqn. (9). Variables f_y and f_c represent the yield strength of the reinforcing steel and the compressive strength of concrete, respectively.

$$M_E = \Theta_E \frac{(g_{sw} + g_{nspl} + \Theta_q q)DL^2}{8} \quad (6)$$

$$M_R = \Theta_R b \rho_s d^2 f_y \left(1 - 0.5 \rho_s \frac{f_y}{f_c}\right) \quad (7)$$

$$b = \begin{cases} b_w & (A) \\ b_{eff} & (B) \end{cases} \quad (8)$$

$$\rho_s = \begin{cases} \rho_{s,w} = \frac{A_s}{b_w d} & (A) \\ \rho_{s,eff} = \frac{A_s}{b_{eff} d} & (B) \end{cases} \quad (9)$$

3.3 Characteristic values

With the aim to define a representative set of design situations, the parameters most relevant to the design of the concrete floor beams are varied within reasonable ranges.

Three spans L are distinguished (6, 12 and 18 m) in addition to four different spacings D between members ($L/1, L/2, L/3, L/4$) (Figure 3). The beams effective cross-section depth d is kept constant equal to $L/15$. A nominal concrete cover to the tensile reinforcement of 30 mm is adopted. Reinforcing steel grade B500 ($f_{yk} = 500 \text{ N/mm}^2$) is assumed in combination with concrete of type C20/25 ($f_{ck}=20 \text{ N/mm}^2$).

In line with EN1991-1-1 [15], a characteristic value of the imposed load of $q_k = 3 \text{ kN/m}^2$ is adopted. A wide range of ratios a_q of variable (q_k) to total (g_k+q_k) characteristic loads between 0.05 and 0.95 is considered, with an interval size $\Delta a_q=0.05$. In addition, three ratios a_g of structural self-weight $g_{sw,k}$ to total permanent loads ($g_{sw,k}+ g_{nspl,k}$) ranging between 0.6 and 1.0 are adopted ($\Delta a_g=0.2$). Based on these assumptions, $g_{sw,k}$ and $g_{nspl,k}$ are computed.

An array for beam tensile reinforcement ratios $\rho_{s,w}$ varying from $\rho_{s,w} = 0.002$ to 0.03 ($\Delta a_q=0.004$) is defined, within the limits of the prescribed $\rho_{s,w,min}$ and $\rho_{s,w,max}$ thresholds according to EN 1992-1-1 [14]. Note that for system B, this results in a corresponding $\rho_{s,eff}$ array ($\rho_{s,eff} = \rho_{s,w} b_w/b_{eff}$).

3.4 Eurocode design

Given the characteristic values described under section 3.3, a strict Eurocode design ($M_{Ed} = M_{Rd}$) of the beam's mid-span cross-section is performed based on the Partial Factor Method (PFM) according to EN1990 [12], with partial factors for f_c and f_y taken from EN1992-1-1 [14]. This results in the strictly required cross-section width b , see Eqn. (8) - note that in case of system B, the design procedure is iterative. The geometry of the beam is thereby established, allowing for a distinction of the structural self-weight of beam and slab, respectively. The depth of the latter, h_{sl} , can then be inferred under the assumption of typical densities for RC members ($\rho_{sl}=2500 \text{ kg/m}^3$).

In order to confine the scope of the study to practically relevant design situations, maximum and minimum slab depth to span ratios (h_{sl}/D) are imposed, as specified in Table 1. In addition, a minimum slab depth h_{sl} of 100 mm is required. Furthermore, boundaries for the ratio of effective beam cross-section depth (d) to width (b_w) are

specified (Table 1). Finally, it is ensured that only ductile cross-sections complying with a $x/d < 0.45$ are considered, where x is the neutral axis depth of the mid-span cross-section.

Table 1. Boundary conditions for selection of design situations included in the study

Variable	min	max
h_{sl}/D	20	30
h_{sl} [mm]	100	-
d/b_w	1	5

For system A, the latter of the described boundary conditions is the most stringent and only 24 relevant design situations are identified. For system B, where the contribution of the flange to the compression forces in the concrete leads generally to relatively small neutral axis depths x (generally $x < h_{fl}$), a total of 145 design situations comply with the imposed boundary conditions.

3.5 Risk-informed design

3.5.1 Decision parameter

In the risk-based optimisation of the RC beams, the dimensions of the, respectively, 24 (system A) and 145 (system B), concrete cross-sections obtained in the Eurocode design (section 3.4) are adopted. The decision parameter (p) corresponds to the optimal amount of tensile reinforcement (A_s) according to the framework established by Eqns. (1) to (5). The corresponding assumptions are described below.

3.5.2 Construction-related emissions

Construction-related carbon emissions CE_c according to Eqn. (2) are specified by Eqn. (10) as the sum of the contribution of concrete (c) and reinforcing steel (s), respectively. These respective contributions are computed as the product of the material mass $M (=V\rho)$, where $\rho_c = 2400 \text{ kg/m}^3$ and $\rho_s = 7850 \text{ kg/m}^3$ and the corresponding carbon emission intensities (CEI_c and CEI_s). Since the optimisation procedure is limited to the beam, V_c excludes the volume of the RC slabs in system A, i.e. $V_c = V_{c,b}$ (concrete volume of the beam), while the emissions embodied in the RC slabs are accounted for in the indirect failure costs term, see section 3.5.3. In system B, however, the slab (i.e. the flange of the T-beam) contributes to the resistance

mechanism of the beam and is hence included in CE_c , i.e. $V_c = V_{c,b+sl}$. Note that the term $V_{c,b+sl}\rho_c CEI_c$ in Eqn. (10) corresponds to the p -independent component C_0 in Eqn. (2).

The emission intensities for concrete, CEI_c and reinforcing steel, CEI_s , reflect cradle-to-gate emissions and have been adopted or inferred from Environmental Product Declarations (EPD) according to EN 15804, issued by the German Institute for Construction and Environment (IBU) [16]. The values are given in Table 2.

$$CE_c = \begin{cases} V_{c,b}\rho_c CEI_c + V_s\rho_s CEI_s & (A) \\ V_{c,b+sl}\rho_c CEI_c + V_s\rho_s CEI_s & (B) \end{cases} \quad (10)$$

3.5.3 Failure emissions

The study considers carbon emissions in consequence of beam failure, CE_f , see Eqn. (4). In addition to those embodied in the re-constructed system (after failure), considered in Eqn. (10), indirect failure emissions H need to be accounted for. These are estimated according to Eqns. (11) and (12) as the sum of the emissions embodied in: the collapsed RC slabs (only for system A following the explanation given in section 3.5.2), the non-structural permanent loads g_{nspl} , i.e. the flooring and roofing systems attached to the slabs, and the non-permanent building equipment, such as furniture or movable partitions. The latter is approximated as a function of the 5 year mean value of the sustained load contribution in office buildings, $q_s = 0.5 \text{ kN/m}^2$, according to [17].

$$H = c_e A_{col} \quad (11)$$

$$c_e = \begin{cases} g_{sw,sl} CEI_{sl} + g_{nspl} CEI_{nspl} + q_s CEI_{q,s} & (A) \\ g_{nspl} CEI_{nspl} + q_s CEI_{q,s} & (B) \end{cases} \quad (12)$$

In Eqn. (11), A_{col} denotes the area affected by the collapse of a beam, which, for both systems (A and B) is approximated as $A_{col} = 4LD$ (floor area supported by and below the collapsing beam). The CEI involved in Eqn. (12) are given in Table 2. The value for the RC slabs (system A) represents a weighted average of CEI_c and CEI_s , whereas the value for non-structural permanent loads, CEI_{nspl} , corresponds to an average out of 32 different configurations of such loads, comprising four different flooring (ceramic tiles + screed, laminate + screed, PEC floor + screed, raised floor) and

roofing systems (suspended ceiling, plaster boards, mineral boards, metal ceiling, in all cases incl. metal ducts for ventilation or installations), respectively. Each of the system components is represented by two different EPDs retrieved from [16]. This procedure leads to a weighted average value of $CEI_{nsp1} = 1.13 \text{ kgCO}_{2,eq}/\text{kg}$ (weighted with regard to the contribution of each component to the total weight of flooring and roofing system).

The carbon emission intensity corresponding to non-permanent building equipment, $CEI_{q,s} = 1.65 \text{ kgCO}_{2,eq}/\text{kg}$, has been estimated as an average value of the CEI reflected in a variety of EPDs for different furniture types (e.g. office chair, desks, shelves, meeting tables), compiled in [18].

Table 2. Carbon emission intensities [$\text{kgCO}_{2,eq}/\text{kg}$]

CEI_c	CEI_s	CEI_{sl}	CEI_{nsp1}	$CEI_{q,s}$
0.074	1.23	0.12	1.13	1.65

3.5.4 Obsolescence and interest rate

The calculation of expected emissions due to structural obsolescence CE_o based on Eqn. (3) assumes an annual obsolescence rate $\omega = 1/50$. The considered annual discount rate i is 3 %.

3.5.5 Probabilistic models

The probabilistic models for the loads (g_{sw}, g_{nsp1}, q), material strengths (f_y, f_c) and model uncertainties ($\Theta_E, \Theta_R, \Theta_q$) are adopted from [17]. All other variables are assumed as deterministic quantities.

3.6 Results

The difference $\delta_{CE_{tot}}$ (see Figure 1) between the expected value of the total emissions corresponding to, respectively, the optimised (OPT) and the Eurocode (EC) solution, is depicted in Figure 5 depending on the ratio of variable to total loads a_q , which is found to range between 0.2 and 0.45 (System A, Figure 5a) and 0.15 and 0.5 (System B, Figure 5b), respectively – design situations with smaller or larger a_q led to non-compliance with the imposed boundary conditions described in section 3.4.). In both systems, A and B, the obtained $\delta_{CE_{tot}}$ are of the same order. For system A, a mean value $\delta_{CE_{tot}}$ of around 2% is found, the maximum reaches

nearly 4%. The corresponding mean and max values for system B are <1% and approximately 2%.

With respect to the EC solution, the optimisation entails *significant material (reinforcement) and emission reductions at the design stage* of the floor systems. This can be observed in Figure 6, which shows the difference δ_p (Figure 1) between the realisations of the decision parameter p according to EC and optimised design, respectively. In case of system A, δ_p attains on average about 10%, with a maximum of up to 15%. Similarly, for the T-beam system (B), mean and max δ_p are around 7% and 13%, respectively. In all cases $\delta_p > 0$, i.e. $p_{EC} > p_{OPT}$ (Figure 1). Accordingly, the optimal (annual) reliability indices β_{OPT} are in all cases below the corresponding β_{EC} values. As Figure 7 shows, β_{OPT} vary between around 3.9 and 4.4 for system A, and between 3.8 and 4.5 for system B. For larger a_q ratios the difference between β_{OPT} and β_{EC} diminishes and so does the saving potential δ_p .

Figure 5. Savings $\delta_{CE_{tot}}$ in terms of expected total emissions CE_{tot} . a) System A; b) System B

Figure 6. Savings δ_p in terms of reinforcement consumption and associated emissions at the design stage. a) System A; b) System B

Figure 7. Annual ($T_{ref} = 1y$) reliability index β corresponding to Eurocode (EC) and optimal (OPT) design. a) System A; b) System B

3.7 Discussion

3.7.1 Emission saving potential

The results presented in Figure 5 point to a relatively low saving potential of the risk-based optimisation (with respect to the EC solution) in terms of the total expected carbon-emissions, CE_{tot} . The reason for this is that emission savings at the design stage, due to lower material consumption, are partially offset by increased failure-emissions, due to lower structural safety levels, i.e. those emissions which arise in case of a structural failure event and the corresponding need for reconstruction of the floor system and the replacement of both permanent and non-permanent building equipment affected by the collapse.

While this appears to be at first sight a sobering observation, the promising result is that the potential emission savings at the design stage, δ_p , are found to be significant. Given the need for urgent measures to reduce embodied greenhouse gas emissions in constructions, the opportunity for potential “immediate” emission reductions of the order of $\delta_p = 7\text{-}10\%$ (average of results in Figure 6), achieved through application of advanced and rational structural safety concepts in structural design procedures, should not be ignored. In any case, it should be ensured that the safety level exceeds the human safety requirements (section 2.2). According to the results shown in Figure 7, it might be possible that this is not fulfilled in all analysed situations. In this case, the corresponding

δ_p are expected to decrease *slightly* when imposing human safety constraints to the failure probability (Figure 2). However, given the large amount of structures erected every day all over the globe, the resource- and emission saving potential with respect to a standardised Eurocode design is, even then, to be judged as large, at least when assessed in absolute terms.

3.7.2 Limitations and outlook

The presented case study is limited to a specific set of design situations comprising reinforced concrete members. A similar study on the flexural design of steel beams supporting prestressed hollow-core slabs in buildings [11] revealed similar results as found herein. Future studies should assess to which extent these findings can be extrapolated to design situations characterised by other failure modes and loading scenarios, including situations governed by environmental loads, such as snow and wind.

In addition, future efforts should be dedicated to overcome the problem that, due to their inherent complexity, risk-based approaches are not suited for application in daily structural design procedures. One way to deal with this problem is to use such approaches as a basis for the calibration of simplified decision rules, such as the Partial Factor method defined in the Eurocodes. See [10] for further discussion of risk-based calibration of structural design codes under consideration of environmental objectives.

4 Conclusions

The development of sustainable built environment systems (e.g. buildings, infrastructures), in general, and for the loadbearing part of such systems (i.e. structures), in particular, within a framework of limited resources and a strong need for mitigation of greenhouse gas emissions, requires substantial modifications at the systemic level of the rules and regulations, which implicitly control most structural engineering decisions. Its high level of detail in regard to the representation of the decision problem and the associated ability to identify optimal design solutions, makes explicit risk-informed decision analysis an appropriate tool for this purpose.

A case study involving the design of RC floor systems has illustrated this. The results underline the significant resource- and greenhouse gas emission saving potential of such approaches in structural design procedures. Future studies should increase the scope of the study to other materials, failure modes and loading scenarios, providing the basis for a consistent risk-based calibration of the standardised design rules and hence for a broad implementation of sustainability principles in structural engineering decision making.

5 Acknowledgements

This study has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 893527.

6 References

- [1] Joint Committee on the Globe Consensus (Globe). *Decarbonizing global construction - Draft*, September 2022, <http://globe-consensus.com>.
- [2] Gibbons OP, Orr JJ. *How to calculate embodied carbon*. The Institution of Structural Engineers. 2022, <https://www.istructe.org>
- [3] De Wolf C, Yang F, Cox D, Charlson A, Hattan AS, Ochsendorf J. Material quantities and embodied carbon dioxide in structures. *Proceedings of the Institution of Civil Engineers - Engineering Sustainability*. 2016;**169**(4):150-61.
- [4] Collings D. The Carbon Footprint of Bridges. *Structural Engineering International*. 2022;**32**(4):501-6.
- [5] Rackwitz R. Optimization — the basis of code-making and reliability verification. *Structural Safety*. 2000;**22**(1):27-60.
- [6] Rackwitz R, Lentz A, Faber M. Socio-economically sustainable civil engineering infrastructures by optimization. *Structural Safety*. 2005;**27**(3):187-229.
- [7] Fischer K, Viljoen C, Köhler J, Faber MH. Optimal and acceptable reliabilities for structural design. *Structural Safety*. 2019;**76**:149-61.
- [8] Köhler J, Baravalle M. Risk-based decision making and the calibration of structural design codes – prospects and challenges. *Civil Engineering and Environmental Systems*. 2019;**36**(1):55-72.
- [9] ISO 2394. *General principles on reliability for structures*, 4th edition. International Organization for Standardization (ISO); 2015.
- [10] Hingorani R, Köhler J. Towards optimized decisions for resource and carbon-efficient structural design (DOI: 10.1080/10286608.2023.2198767). *Civil Engineering and Environmental Systems*. 2023.
- [11] Hingorani R, Köhler J. Sustainability potential of risk-informed decisions in structural design (Paper accepted for publication). 14th *International Conference on Application of Statistics and Probability in Civil Engineering*; Dublin, 2023.
- [12] EN 1990. *Eurocode - Basis of structural design*. Brussels: European Committee for Standardization; 2002.
- [13] Adhikari P, Mahmoud H, Xie A, Simonen K, Ellingwood B. Life-cycle cost and carbon footprint analysis for light-framed residential buildings subjected to tornado hazard. *Journal of Building Engineering*. 2020;**32**:101657.
- [14] EN 1992-1-1. *Eurocode 2: Design of concrete structures - Part 1-1: General rules and rules for buildings*. Brussels: European Committee for Standardization; 2004.
- [15] EN 1991-1-1. *Eurocode. Actions on structures. General actions – Densities, selfweight, imposed loads for buildings*. Brussels: European Committee for Standardization; 2002.
- [16] *Institut Bauen und Umwelt (IBU)*. 2023. Available from: <http://www.ibu-epd.com>.
- [17] CEN TC 250 SC10 N 5553. *JRC report - Reliability background of the Eurocodes - Draft 2022-02-11* Rotterdam; 2022.
- [18] Jortveit Lauvland H. *The Carbon Footprint of Furniture* (Master Thesis): Norwegian University of Science and Technology (NTNU); 2021.